

**Designing a Roadmap for
Effective and Sustainable Strategies for
Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of
EU Agriculture to Navigate within a
Safe and Just Operating Space**

**Income and Price Elasticities of
Demand for Food in the EU**

Discussion paper

AUTHORS	Esther Gehrke (WU), Yan Jin (WU)
CALL	Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal
WORK PROGRAMME Topic ID	EU agriculture within a safe and just operating space and planetary boundaries HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-12
PROJECT WEB SITE:	https://brightspace-project.eu/

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 101060075 for the European Commission. It does not necessarily reflect the view of the European Union and in no way anticipates the Commission's future policy in this area.

Income and Price Elasticities of Demand for Food in the EU *

Esther Gehrke [†] Yan Jin [‡]

April 13, 2026

Abstract

Using representative cross-sectional household survey data from the 27 EU member states, this paper estimates consumer demand elasticities at the EU level, by quintiles of household income, and at the member state level. It employs an EASI demand system, imposing weak separability between consumption expenditures and other expenditures. At the aggregated EU level, all food categories behave as normal goods. Own-price elasticities are negative for all food categories but differ in magnitude: potatoes, milk and dairy products, and fruits are relatively price responsive, while fish and seafood, poultry and eggs, bread, and meat are less sensitive to price changes. Demand elasticities vary considerably by income level, with poorer households being more price sensitive overall. *JEL: D12, C31, Q11*

Keywords: EASI demand system, income elasticity, price elasticity of demand, policy simulation, European Union

*We are grateful to Michiel van Dijk for useful comments. Teun van Dommelen provided excellent research assistance. Funding from the EU [grant number 101060075] is gratefully acknowledged.

[†]Corresponding author. Wageningen University and Research, Agricultural Economics and Rural Policy, Hollandseweg 1, 6709KN Wageningen, The Netherlands. E-mail: *esther.gehrke@wur.nl*

[‡]Wageningen University and Research, Agricultural Economics and Rural Policy, Hollandseweg 1, 6709KN Wageningen, The Netherlands; Wageningen Social & Economic Research, Department of International Policy, Prinses Beatrixlaan 582, 2595BM, The Hague, The Netherlands. E-mail: *yan.jin@wur.nl*

1 Introduction

Food systems in the European Union (EU) are increasingly recognized as a major driver of global environmental change, contributing substantially to greenhouse gas emissions, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation (Willett et al., 2019). To remain within planetary boundaries, a fundamental transformation of food consumption and production patterns is required (Gerten et al., 2020). One policy instrument that has gained considerable attention is the use of carbon taxes on relatively emission-intensive foods, potentially combined with subsidies for healthier and more climate-friendly alternatives. Such policies aim to simultaneously reduce environmental pressures and improve nutrition outcomes.

Achieving these dual objectives is challenging. Nutrition security, defined as access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that supports a healthy and active life (Committee on World Food Security, 2012), remains an issue within the EU, where 6.6% of the population was moderately or severely nutrition insecure in 2021 (World Health Organization et al., 2022). Policies that alter food prices can therefore have uneven effects across households, raising concerns about distributional impacts and health outcomes. Understanding how consumers respond to price changes is thus central to evaluating the effectiveness and equity of carbon pricing in the food system.

Ex-ante modeling is commonly used to inform such policy design. Large-scale equilibrium models (e.g., CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET-GTAP) capture economy-wide effects of agricultural and environmental policies but typically rely on a representative household for each country, thereby abstracting from heterogeneity in consumer behavior (Latka et al., 2021). Yet, households differ markedly in dietary needs, financial constraints, and preferences, all of which shape consumption responses. Ignoring this heterogeneity can lead to biased predictions of policy impacts.

This paper estimates consumer income and price elasticities of demand for the EU while explicitly accounting for heterogeneity in preferences across households. Using cross-sectional data from the EU Household Budget Survey, we estimate price and income elasticities across ten food categories in EU countries and examine how variation in income shapes responses to food price changes. These elasticity estimates can then be used to simulate the effects of a hypothetical carbon tax or other policy changes on food consumption patterns and associated health outcomes. By uncovering response heterogeneity at the EU level, this paper provides a more realistic basis for assessing the environmental and nutritional implications of policy changes.

The remainder of this paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 describes the empirical strategy and data, Section 3 presents the results, and Section 4 concludes.

2 Empirical Strategy

2.1 Exact Affine Stone Index (EASI) Demand System Estimation

Household demand models applied in policy analysis need to be consistent with consumer theory. Demand models have experienced modifications over time. Currently, the EASI demand system is considered to be the most advanced demand estimation system over traditional approaches, such as the linear expenditure system (LES) (Stone, 1954), the Almost Ideal Demand System (AIDS) (Deaton and Muellbauer, 1980), and the Quadratic Almost Ideal Demand System (QUAIDS) (Banks et al., 1997). The EASI demand system is widely used in estimating income (expenditure) and price elasticities of demand, which are further used for policy simulations, such as the minimum pricing policy for the consumption of soft drinks in Mexico (Dogbe and Revoredo-Giha, 2026), the carbon tax on food in Europe (Dogbe et al., 2024; Tovar Reaños and Lynch, 2023), and the electricity tax in Colombia (Ramírez-Hassan and López-Vera, 2024).

Unlike traditional demand systems, the EASI demand system offers advantages by providing greater flexibility in modeling Engel curves while allowing the error terms to be interpreted as unobserved household preference heterogeneity. Furthermore, the expenditure-function foundation of the model facilitates welfare analysis and the computation of policy-relevant welfare metrics (Lewbel and Pendakur, 2009).

Given the advantages of the EASI demand system, we employ this framework. We assume that household h with observable characteristics $\mathbf{z}_h = (z_{h,1}, \dots, z_{h,L})'$ and log-nominal total food expenditures x_h chooses a bundle of J food categories as a function of the vector of prices $\mathbf{p}_h = (p_{h,1}, \dots, p_{h,J})'$. Following Lewbel and Pendakur (2009), the household's cost function can be expressed as $x_h = C(\mathbf{p}_h, u_h, \mathbf{z}_h, \varepsilon_h)$, where $\varepsilon_h = (\varepsilon_{h,1}, \dots, \varepsilon_{h,J})'$ is a vector of household and food category specific preference shifters. The cost function represents the minimum expenditures necessary for household h to realize utility u_h . Replacing utility with implicit utility y_h , and taking the first order derivative, leads to the implicit Marshallian demand functions $w_h = \omega(\mathbf{p}_h, y_h, \mathbf{z}_h, \varepsilon_h)$.

Approximating implicit utility with log nominal expenditures x_h deflated by the log Stone price index $\mathbf{p}_h' \mathbf{w}_h$, such that $y_h = x_h - \mathbf{p}_h' \mathbf{w}_h$, allows estimating a system of budget share equations \mathbf{w}_h that are linear in parameters:

$$\mathbf{w}_h = \sum_{r=1}^{R=4} \mathbf{b}_r y_h^r + \mathbf{A} p_h + \mathbf{B} p_h y_h + \sum_{l=1}^{L=5} (\mathbf{C}_l z_{l,h} + \mathbf{D}_l z_{l,h} y_h) + \sum_{l=1}^{L=5} \mathbf{E}_l z_{l,h} p_h + \varepsilon_h,$$

where \mathbf{w}_h is the J -vector of budget shares that household h spends on the J food categories.

Lewbel and Pendakur (2009) demonstrate that the linear approximation yields estimates that do not differ substantially from those obtained from the exact system, even though that approximation may introduce endogeneity. However, the common Stone price index provides a computationally convenient approximation to the exact price aggregator, substantially simplifying estimation while preserving the empirical performance of the EASI demand system.

The estimation equation contains a fourth-order polynomial in y_h and $L=5$ different demographic characteristics $z_{l,h}$, and $J = 10$ different log-prices $p_{h,j}$. ε_h indicates unobservable preference characteristics. $\mathbf{b} = (b_1, \dots, b_4)'$, $\mathbf{A} = (A_1, \dots, A_J)'$, and $\mathbf{B} = (B_1, \dots, B_J)'$ are parameter vectors and \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{D} , and \mathbf{E} are parameter matrices to be estimated. The five demographic characteristics are indicators taking the value of one if (1) the household head is older than 45, (2) the household head is male, (3) there are children in the household, (4) household income is above the country-median, and (5) the household is located in a high population density area, respectively.

Following Plinke et al. (2026), we estimate the linear approximation of the EASI demand system using sample-weighted seemingly unrelated regression (SUR). We estimate partial demand systems that rely on the assumption of weak separability between food and non-food consumption (Gorman, 1959). Specifically, households first allocate expenditure across broad consumption groups and then determine the optimal allocation of goods within each group given the allocated category budget; therefore, we assume that households' nominal food expenditures remain constant in response to food price changes following the literature (Jin and Gil, 2025; Roosen et al., 2022; Dogbe and Gil, 2018).

The income (expenditure) elasticity η_h^{EE} and the Hicksian (compensated) price elasticity of demand η_h^{PE} can be calculated based on the equations below, following the approach of (Pendakur, 2009; Lewbel and Pendakur, 2009).

$$\eta_h^{EE} = \tilde{\omega}_h^{-1} \hat{\Phi}_h \left[\sum_{r=0}^{R=4} b_r y_h^r + \mathbf{B} p_h + \mathbf{D} z_h \right] + \mathbf{1}_n$$

where η_h^{EE} is the $J \times 1$ -vector of compensated income elasticities of household h , indicating the percentage change in demand when real expenditure y increases by 1%.

$$\eta_h^{PE} = \tilde{\omega}_h^{-1} \hat{\Phi}_h [\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B} y_h] + \tilde{\omega}_h - I$$

η_h^{PE} denotes a $J \times J$ matrix of compensated price elasticities for household h . The matrix $\tilde{\omega}_h$ is a modified identity matrix in which the diagonal elements are replaced by the budget shares \mathbf{w}_h of household h , and I denotes the $J \times J$ identity matrix.

Hicksian elasticities are converted into Marshallian (uncompensated) elasticities using the Slutsky equation. Marshallian elasticities include both substitution and income effects and are employed in the policy analysis to measure the percentage change in quantity demanded following price changes (Lewbel and Pendakur, 2009).

2.2 Data

This study closely follows the data construction and imputation strategy developed by Plinke et al. (2026). To estimate country-specific food demand systems, we primarily rely on the Eurostat Household Budget Survey (HBS) for the reference years 2020, 2015, and 2010, covering 26 of the 27 EU Member States. These harmonized datasets are based on national household surveys conducted by national statistical offices during 2018-2022 (for the 2020 wave), 2014–2016 (for the 2015 wave) and 2008–2012 (for the 2010 wave). All expenditure values are converted to euros of the respective HBS reference year using Eurostat price adjustment coefficients. As no quantities or expenditures are available for Germany in the HBS dataset, we complement this data with scientific use files of the Einkommens- und Verbrauchsstichprobe (EVS) 2018 provided by the German Federal Statistical Office.

As such, the data used here cover 27 representative cross-sectional household surveys. Across all countries, food expenditures are recorded using household diaries over a fixed reporting period ranging from two weeks to three months and classified according to the UN Classification of Individual Consumption by Purpose (COICOP). In addition, the surveys include key sociodemographic and income variables at the household level.

For each country, we use the most recent survey wave that reports both expenditures and quantities for food items. For Member States for which none of the three HBS rounds contain expenditures and quantities at the food item level, we impute missing quantities as described below. The resulting choice of HBS round per country is reported in Table 1.

Treatment of missing quantity information

Two types of missing quantity information are addressed. First, in some countries, quantities for certain food items are not recorded at all. Second, some households report positive expenditures but zero quantities for specific items. Following Plinke et al. (2026), these cases are treated separately using nearest-neighbor imputation techniques.

When quantity data are structurally missing at the country level (only expenditure data reported), we apply a cross-country matching approach. Countries are grouped into four European regions (north, east, south, and west). For each household with positive expenditures, missing quantities are imputed using a pool of households from the same region that

report quantities for the relevant item. Ten nearest neighbors are selected based on sociodemographic characteristics, income, and item-specific expenditures, and imputed quantities are calculated as a distance-weighted mean adjusted for expenditure differences. Households with zero expenditures are assigned zero quantities.

When quantities are zero and expenditures non-zero for individual households and food categories, we perform a within-country matching procedure. Households with positive expenditures but zero quantities are matched to similar households within the same country that report both positive expenditures and quantities for the relevant item, using the same nearest-neighbor methodology.

Prices

Prices are recovered at the item level by dividing expenditures for any item by the quantities purchased of that same item. To remove outliers, these prices are then winsorized at three times the interquartile range (IQR) at the country by food-item level. Missing prices for households who did not consume any given food item (quantity equals zero) are imputed with the country median price (Roosen et al., 2022).

This approach of computing prices ignores potential quality differences within food groups. This may bias estimated elasticities if it introduces systematic correlation between computed prices (unit values) and unobserved household characteristics. However, we expect quality to be mainly correlated with income and expenditures (as richer households may demand higher quality goods), which we control for in the analysis.

Final sample

Food expenditures are then aggregated from five-digit COICOP items into ten food categories, namely (1) Bread and cereals, (2) Potatoes, roots and tubers, (3) Vegetables, (4) Fruits, (5) Fish and seafood, (6) Milk and dairy, (7) Poultry and eggs, (8) Meat (excl. poultry), (9) Oils and fats, and (10) Food not elsewhere classified (NEC) including sugar. To construct mean prices at the food category level, we weight item-level unit values by expenditures per item.

Final exclusions apply to households with exceptionally high food budget shares (above 75%) and those with zero food expenditures after imputation. Households reporting implausible observations at the five-digit COICOP level, specifically negative expenditures or positive quantities combined with zero expenditures, are also excluded from the sample.

3 Results

Using the resulting harmonized dataset for the 27 EU Member States, we estimate a LA-EASI demand system for all Member States combined, as well as separate systems for each Member State to obtain country-specific price and income elasticity estimates for the ten food categories. We use a different food category aggregation than [Plinke et al. \(2026\)](#), as we are interested in the health implications of changing diets; therefore, a higher granularity at the vegetable and fruit level is introduced.

3.1 EU-level aggregates

Based on the data provided in [Table 2](#) for the EU27, we summarize the estimates of the expenditure elasticities and uncompensated (Marshallian) price elasticities of demand in [Table 3](#), which reveal distinct consumption patterns across food categories. All expenditure elasticities (last column of [Table 3](#)) are positive and close to 1.0, suggesting that these food categories are “normal goods.” Vegetables (1.110), potatoes, roots, tubers (1.068), fruits (1.061), and oils and fats (1.016) are the most income-elastic, meaning demand for these items grows slightly more than proportionately as total food expenditure increases. In contrast, consumption of items in the residual group (0.905), of bread and cereals (0.935), and milk and dairy (0.947) increases less than proportional in income.

The own-price elasticities (highlighted in bold along the diagonal) are all negative, consistent with the economic theory that a higher price would lead to a lower demand, but the magnitude of own-price elasticities varies. Our estimates are similar to those in the literature, such as [Plinke et al. \(2026\)](#), [Bonnet et al. \(2018\)](#), and [Roosen et al. \(2022\)](#). The most price-sensitive food categories include potatoes, roots, tubers (-0.991), milk and dairy (-0.893), and fruits (-0.871), which show the largest elasticities in absolute terms. For these goods, a price increase leads to a relatively large reduction in quantity demanded. The least price-sensitive food categories include fish and seafood (-0.670), poultry and eggs (-0.684), bread and cereals (-0.760), and meat (-0.760), exhibiting the lowest elasticities, which suggests that these food categories are seen as relatively more stable in the consumption basket or have fewer immediate substitutes. Regarding the cross-price relationships, the off-diagonal values are generally small, indicating weak substitution (positive value) or complementarity (negative value) between categories. For example, the positive value between milk and vegetables (0.032) suggests a very slight substitution effect, while the negative value between milk and bread (-0.016) indicates minor complementary relationships.

As a robustness check, an alternative food aggregation is available in [Table A1](#), which shows a similar pattern in terms of elasticities in various food categories. In the appendix,

Tables [A2-A28](#) show the expenditure elasticities and uncompensated price elasticities of demand in each Member State, respectively. Our results are consistent with [Plinke et al. \(2026\)](#), except that all our expenditure elasticities are positive, while in their study, negative expenditure elasticities exist, such as fish in Austria, Italy, and Poland, and beef in Belgium, Denmark, Italy, and Spain.

3.2 Income Quintiles

To illustrate heterogeneity among different income categories, Tables [4-8](#) show the expenditure elasticities and uncompensated price elasticities of demand for ten food categories across five income quintiles, respectively. Income quintiles are computed within a country before aggregating across countries, and income is divided by OECD equivalent household size to obtain per capita values.¹

Regarding income elasticity across quintiles, in Tables [4-8](#), there is a clear shift in dietary responsiveness. Consistent with Bennett’s Law, we find that lower-income households allocate a larger share of their food budget to staple products (e.g., bread and cereals) and therefore exhibit lower income responsiveness for these items. As income increases toward the upper quintiles, the share of food budget to staple products decreases, and demand for more diverse or higher-value foods becomes more responsive to income changes. For example, food categories such as fruits, vegetables, fish, and poultry maintain expenditure elasticities around or above one across higher quintiles, reflecting a tendency for higher income households to further expand consumption of these items when their food expenditure increases. Although we are not aware of other EU-level demand systems that explicitly focus on income heterogeneity, our findings are consistent with the country-level literature, e.g. [Rathu Manannalage et al. \(2023\)](#); [Shiba et al. \(2025\)](#).

Price elasticities of demand also differ systematically across quintiles. Own-price elasticities are negative for all food categories, consistent with standard demand theory. However, lower-income households tend to exhibit larger absolute price elasticities, meaning their consumption is more sensitive to price changes. For instance, in the lowest quintile, Quintile 1 in Table [4](#), the own-price elasticity for bread and cereals is about -0.809 (compared with -0.720 in Quintile 5 in Table [8](#)), indicating relatively strong responsiveness to price increases. This may be due to tighter budget constraints among poorer households, who must adjust their consumption more strongly when prices change. Our findings are consistent with the literature for low-income households or households in low-income countries [Nzayiramyia et al. \(2025\)](#); [Green et al. \(2013\)](#); [Muhammad et al. \(2017\)](#).

¹The Italy data does not contain income information; in that country, we group households by expenditure quintiles instead.

By contrast, higher-income households show smaller (less negative) price elasticities, implying that their consumption is less sensitive to price fluctuations. This pattern is evident for most food categories, except for fish and meat, where price responses increase slightly in higher quintiles. The potential reasons may include a larger diversity in quality and prices in the fish and seafood category, which would lead richer households to respond more strongly to price changes in the high-end fish market. Another reason may be that wealthier households generally have more flexible budgets and therefore do not need to reduce consumption of fish as strongly when prices rise.

The differences in price-elasticities concerning fruits and vegetables hint at the fact that relatively poor households may benefit the most from tax incentives on healthy food. Households in the lowest income quintile display higher price-sensitivity regarding fruits (-0.888) and vegetables (-0.825) than households in the highest income quintile (-0.852 and -0.725, respectively). While these differences are small, they nevertheless reveal potential for substantial health benefits of tax reforms.

In summary, the quintile analysis highlights the heterogeneity in consumer behavior across income groups. Lower-income households are, in general, more price sensitive and allocate a greater share of their expenditure to staple foods, while higher-income households exhibit greater income responsiveness for higher-value foods and weaker responses to price changes. These differences imply that policies affecting food prices, such as carbon taxes or food subsidies, may have unequal impacts across income groups. Policy makers should consider the distributional effects as well as the potential health gains of food policies.

4 Conclusions

This paper estimates income and price elasticities of food demand for the European Union using the EASI demand system based on harmonized microdata from the Household Budget Survey and the EVS covering all 27 EU Member States. By exploiting repeated cross-sectional household data, we study how consumers respond to changes in food prices and expenditures, and provide new evidence on heterogeneity across income groups at the EU level. These estimates set an empirical basis for evaluating food policies that operate through price changes, including fiscal instruments aimed at promoting healthier and more sustainable diets.

At the aggregated EU level, all food categories behave as normal goods. Own-price elasticities are negative for all food categories but differ in magnitude: potatoes, milk and dairy products, and fruits are relatively price responsive, while fish and seafood, poultry and eggs, bread, and meat are less sensitive to price changes. Cross-price elasticities are

generally small, implying limited substitution across broad food categories and indicating that consumers tend to adjust consumption within categories rather than shifting strongly between them when prices change.

There exists heterogeneity across income groups. Lower-income households allocate a larger share of their food budget to staple foods and exhibit greater sensitivity to price changes. Higher-income households, on the contrary, show stronger expenditure responsiveness for higher-value foods such as fruits, vegetables, fish, and poultry, while their price elasticities tend to be smaller in magnitude. These results highlight the role of income in shaping dietary patterns and demand responses. Therefore, accounting for this heterogeneity is important when evaluating the impacts of food policy interventions.

Overall, we suggest that demand estimates at an aggregated level can obscure important differences across households, and the elasticity estimates across various income groups provide a sound base in their consumption module for large-scale equilibrium models and are valuable for ex-ante policy simulations in general to assess the effects of price-based interventions on food consumption, nutrition, and environmental outcomes in the EU. Policy instruments, such as taxes on emission-intensive foods, can influence household consumption patterns and promote more sustainable diets; however, due to the heterogeneous price responsiveness across income groups, there is a need for complementary measures like targeted transfers or subsidies for healthier foods to mitigate potential distributional impacts.

Bibliography

- Banks, J., R. Blundell, and A. Lewbel (1997). Quadratic engel curves and consumer demand. *Review of Economics and statistics* 79(4), 527–539.
- Bonnet, C., Z. Bouamra-Mechemache, and T. Corre (2018). An environmental tax towards more sustainable food: empirical evidence of the consumption of animal products in france. *Ecological economics* 147, 48–61.
- Committee on World Food Security (2012). Global strategic framework for food security and nutrition.
- Deaton, A. and J. Muellbauer (1980). An almost ideal demand system. *The American economic review* 70(3), 312–326.
- Dogbe, W., F. Akaichi, V. Rungapamestry, and C. Revoredo-Giha (2024). Effectiveness of implemented global dietary interventions: a scoping review of fiscal policies. *BMC Public Health* 24(1), 2552.
- Dogbe, W. and J. M. Gil (2018). Effectiveness of a carbon tax to promote a climate-friendly food consumption. *Food Policy* 79, 235–246.
- Dogbe, W. and C. Revoredo-Giha (2026). Effectiveness of a minimum pricing policy for the consumption of soft drinks in mexico. *Food Policy* 138, 102997.
- Gerten, D., V. Heck, J. Jägermeyr, B. L. Bodirsky, I. Fetzer, M. Jalava, M. Kummu, W. Lucht, J. Rockström, S. Schaphoff, and H. J. Schellnhuber (2020). Feeding ten billion people is possible within four terrestrial planetary boundaries. *Nature Sustainability* 3, 200–208.
- Gorman, W. M. (1959). Separable utility and aggregation. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, 469–481.
- Green, R., L. Cornelsen, A. D. Dangour, R. Turner, B. Shankar, M. Mazzocchi, and R. D. Smith (2013). The effect of rising food prices on food consumption: systematic review with meta-regression. *Bmj* 346.
- Jin, Y. and J. M. Gil (2025). Are consumers more sensitive to price changes during food scares? a regime-switching dynamic almost ideal demand system approach. *Agricultural and Food Economics* 13(1), 44.

- Latka, C., M. Kuiper, S. Frank, T. Heckelei, P. Havlík, H.-P. Witzke, A. Leip, H. D. Cui, A. Kuijsten, J. M. Geleijnse, et al. (2021). Paying the price for environmentally sustainable and healthy eu diets. *Global Food Security* 28, 100437.
- Lewbel, A. and K. Pendakur (2009). Tricks with hicks: The easi demand system. *American Economic Review* 99(3), 827–863.
- Muhammad, A., A. D’Souza, B. Meade, R. Micha, and D. Mozaffarian (2017). The influence of income and prices on global dietary patterns by country, age, and gender. Technical report, United States Department of Agriculture, Economic Research Service.
- Nzayiramy, S., A. Muhammad, and A. Baffoe-Bonnie (2025). A global assessment of food and non-food spending: evidence from 173 countries and implications for food security. *Agriculture & Food Security* 14(1), 20.
- Pendakur, K. (2009). Easi made easier.
- Plinke, C., M. Sureth, and M. Kalkuhl (2026). Environmental impacts from european food consumption can be reduced with carbon pricing or a value-added tax reform. *Nature Food* 7, 74–87.
- Ramírez-Hassan, A. and A. López-Vera (2024). Welfare implications of a tax on electricity: A semi-parametric specification of the incomplete easi demand system. *Energy Economics* 131, 107389.
- Rathu Manannalage, K. M. L., A. Chai, and S. Ratnasiri (2023). Eating to live or living to eat? exploring the link between calorie satiation, bennett’s law, and the evolution of food preferences. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics* 33(4), 1197–1236.
- Roosen, J., M. Staudigel, and S. Rahbauer (2022). Demand elasticities for fresh meat and welfare effects of meat taxes in germany. *Food Policy* 106, 102194.
- Shiba, W. T., M. Aliber, and S. Zantsi (2025). Rural household food expenditure and agriculture: comparison of agricultural and non-agricultural households in south africa. *Development in Practice*, 1–13.
- Stone, R. (1954). Linear expenditure systems and demand analysis: an application to the pattern of british demand. *The Economic Journal* 64(255), 511–527.
- Tovar Reaños, M. A. and M. Á. Lynch (2023). The benefits of action on implementing carbon taxation in ireland: a demand system approach. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management* 66(4), 836–860.

Willett, W., J. Rockström, B. Loken, M. Springmann, T. Lang, S. Vermeulen, T. Garnett, D. Tilman, F. DeClerck, A. Wood, M. Jonell, M. Clark, L. J. Gordon, J. Fanzo, C. Hawkes, R. Zurayk, J. A. Rivera, W. De Vries, L. Majele Sibanda, A. Afshin, A. Chaudhary, M. Herrero, R. Agustina, F. Branca, A. Lartey, S. Fan, B. Crona, E. Fox, V. Bignet, M. Troell, T. Lindahl, S. Singh, S. E. Cornell, K. Srinath Reddy, S. Narain, S. Nishtar, and C. J. L. Murray (2019, feb). Food in the Anthropocene: the EAT–Lancet Commission on healthy diets from sustainable food systems. *The Lancet* 393(10170), 447–492.

World Health Organization et al. (2022). *The state of food security and nutrition in the world 2022: Repurposing food and agricultural policies to make healthy diets more affordable*, Volume 2022. Food & Agriculture Org.

Tables

Table 1: Household Budget Survey (HBS) coverage by country

Country	Code	HBS year used	Quantities available	Region
Austria	AT	2020	Yes	West
Belgium	BE	2020	Yes	West
Bulgaria	BG	2020	Yes	West
Cyprus	CY	2020	No	South
Czech Republic	CZ	2015	Yes	East
Germany	DE	2018	Yes	West
Denmark	DK	2020	No	North
Estonia	EE	2020	Yes	North
Greece	EL	2020	Yes	South
Spain	ES	2020	Yes	South
Finland	FI	2015	Yes	North
France	FR	2010	Yes	West
Croatia	HR	2015	Yes	South
Hungary	HU	2020	Yes	East
Ireland	IE	2010	Yes	North
Italy	IT	2020	No	South
Lithuania	LT	2010	Yes	North
Luxembourg	LU	2020	Yes	West
Latvia	LV	2020	Yes	North
Malta	MT	2020	No	South
Netherlands	NL	2020	No	West
Poland	PL	2020	Yes	East
Portugal	PT	2015	Yes	South
Romania	RO	2015	Yes	East
Sweden	SE	2015	No	North
Slovenia	SI	2015	Yes	South
Slovakia	SK	2020	Yes	East

Note: Data for Germany are from the EVS.

Table 2: Summary Statistics by Food Group

Food Group	Expenditure Shares		Prices (log)	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Bread and cereals	0.184	0.111	1.080	0.565
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.032	0.042	0.770	0.871
Vegetables	0.100	0.071	0.827	0.576
Fruits	0.090	0.076	0.890	0.629
Fish and seafood	0.058	0.079	1.716	0.623
Milk and dairy	0.140	0.081	1.352	0.619
Poultry and Eggs	0.066	0.062	1.253	0.514
Meat	0.190	0.118	1.829	0.478
Oils and fats	0.036	0.040	1.325	0.545
NEC incl. sugar	0.105	0.094	1.661	0.657

Table 3: All EU : Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.760	0.045	-0.071	-0.031	-0.099	-0.022	-0.033	-0.013	-0.063	-0.037	0.935
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.022	-0.991	-0.053	0.004	0.001	-0.002	-0.003	0.015	-0.040	0.010	1.068
Vegetables	-0.024	-0.097	-0.781	-0.009	-0.012	0.044	-0.035	-0.075	0.021	0.010	1.110
Fruits	-0.006	0.004	-0.015	-0.871	-0.022	0.002	-0.053	-0.032	-0.020	0.023	1.061
Fish and seafood	-0.074	-0.005	-0.023	-0.030	-0.670	-0.066	0.009	-0.023	-0.038	-0.058	0.986
Milk and dairy	-0.016	-0.017	0.032	-0.012	-0.070	-0.893	-0.011	0.003	0.028	-0.023	0.947
Poultry and Eggs	-0.013	-0.007	-0.033	-0.042	0.005	-0.004	-0.684	-0.047	-0.055	-0.016	1.000
Meat	-0.012	0.031	-0.167	-0.072	-0.034	0.012	-0.116	-0.760	-0.033	-0.045	0.978
Oils and fats	-0.018	-0.041	0.009	-0.012	-0.017	0.015	-0.039	-0.008	-0.817	0.004	1.016
NEC incl. sugar	-0.035	0.011	-0.008	0.015	-0.069	-0.031	-0.035	-0.038	0.001	-0.773	0.905
Expenditure shares	0.184	0.032	0.100	0.090	0.058	0.140	0.066	0.190	0.036	0.105	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table 4: Quintile 1: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.809	0.063	-0.020	-0.018	-0.096	-0.018	-0.040	-0.033	-0.054	-0.017	0.928
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.028	-1.014	-0.029	0.009	0.001	-0.000	-0.001	-0.004	-0.035	0.012	1.099
Vegetables	0.003	-0.065	-0.825	-0.005	-0.026	0.035	-0.022	-0.070	0.024	-0.007	1.070
Fruits	0.001	0.007	-0.008	-0.888	-0.006	0.007	-0.047	-0.045	-0.009	0.018	1.036
Fish and seafood	-0.065	-0.011	-0.036	-0.016	-0.628	-0.053	0.001	-0.032	-0.021	-0.057	0.937
Milk and dairy	-0.010	-0.018	0.025	-0.001	-0.056	-0.932	-0.013	0.002	0.032	-0.013	0.956
Poultry and Eggs	-0.012	-0.001	-0.019	-0.038	0.005	-0.004	-0.724	-0.036	-0.067	-0.026	1.038
Meat	-0.033	-0.037	-0.146	-0.089	-0.053	0.010	-0.094	-0.724	-0.028	-0.058	0.994
Oils and fats	-0.014	-0.040	0.014	-0.006	-0.008	0.015	-0.046	-0.007	-0.840	-0.002	1.011
NEC incl. sugar	-0.017	0.016	-0.024	0.017	-0.071	-0.017	-0.053	-0.045	-0.013	-0.793	0.943
Expenditure shares	0.201	0.036	0.098	0.079	0.051	0.136	0.074	0.187	0.038	0.100	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table 5: Quintile 2: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.770	0.045	-0.069	-0.019	-0.098	-0.011	-0.044	-0.015	-0.058	-0.039	0.912
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.025	-1.006	-0.033	0.012	0.001	-0.000	-0.007	-0.001	-0.025	0.008	1.127
Vegetables	-0.025	-0.072	-0.818	-0.008	-0.003	0.049	-0.035	-0.064	0.030	0.004	1.083
Fruits	0.005	0.011	-0.012	-0.889	-0.026	0.002	-0.048	-0.037	-0.015	0.024	1.062
Fish and seafood	-0.068	-0.006	-0.015	-0.036	-0.633	-0.062	0.015	-0.030	-0.030	-0.072	0.960
Milk and dairy	-0.001	-0.020	0.046	-0.009	-0.065	-0.916	-0.011	0.006	0.009	-0.036	0.967
Poultry and Eggs	-0.015	-0.016	-0.032	-0.040	0.012	-0.004	-0.709	-0.040	-0.064	-0.014	1.014
Meat	-0.015	-0.032	-0.151	-0.085	-0.046	0.010	-0.103	-0.748	-0.016	-0.045	0.966
Oils and fats	-0.016	-0.029	0.014	-0.010	-0.013	0.005	-0.045	-0.004	-0.808	-0.005	0.997
NEC incl. sugar	-0.031	-0.002	-0.015	0.022	-0.088	-0.040	-0.028	-0.032	-0.020	-0.765	0.941
Expenditure shares	0.189	0.033	0.098	0.086	0.055	0.138	0.068	0.194	0.037	0.102	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table 6: Quintile 3: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.761	0.043	-0.074	-0.047	-0.094	-0.021	-0.033	-0.004	-0.068	-0.045	0.929
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.024	-1.006	-0.052	0.005	0.001	0.002	-0.004	0.011	-0.043	0.015	1.103
Vegetables	-0.025	-0.099	-0.783	-0.019	-0.009	0.054	-0.035	-0.070	0.001	0.013	1.111
Fruits	-0.013	0.001	-0.023	-0.883	-0.018	0.003	-0.050	-0.020	-0.013	0.022	1.083
Fish and seafood	-0.068	-0.008	-0.020	-0.029	-0.657	-0.070	0.013	-0.025	-0.040	-0.058	0.968
Milk and dairy	-0.012	-0.012	0.049	-0.012	-0.073	-0.901	-0.010	-0.007	0.044	-0.025	0.960
Poultry and Eggs	-0.010	-0.011	-0.031	-0.042	0.009	-0.004	-0.688	-0.049	-0.053	-0.011	1.004
Meat	-0.001	0.014	-0.166	-0.057	-0.039	-0.007	-0.132	-0.762	-0.036	-0.043	0.974
Oils and fats	-0.020	-0.042	-0.003	-0.009	-0.017	0.020	-0.040	-0.008	-0.798	0.004	1.009
NEC incl. sugar	-0.043	0.017	-0.010	0.009	-0.070	-0.037	-0.027	-0.039	-0.001	-0.760	0.889
Expenditure shares	0.183	0.031	0.099	0.089	0.058	0.140	0.065	0.194	0.036	0.105	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table 7: Quintile 4: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.746	0.040	-0.111	-0.030	-0.110	-0.030	-0.024	0.010	-0.062	-0.038	0.935
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.020	-0.983	-0.063	0.003	0.007	-0.003	-0.006	0.020	-0.048	0.011	1.053
Vegetables	-0.045	-0.111	-0.778	0.007	-0.005	0.048	-0.043	-0.075	0.022	0.020	1.136
Fruits	-0.006	0.004	0.001	-0.867	-0.027	-0.004	-0.051	-0.033	-0.036	0.025	1.070
Fish and seafood	-0.083	0.010	-0.015	-0.037	-0.679	-0.071	0.013	-0.021	-0.031	-0.053	0.993
Milk and dairy	-0.023	-0.018	0.035	-0.022	-0.076	-0.887	-0.006	0.013	0.020	-0.021	0.942
Poultry and Eggs	-0.011	-0.011	-0.041	-0.042	0.008	-0.002	-0.674	-0.054	-0.044	-0.013	0.987
Meat	0.014	0.054	-0.175	-0.077	-0.032	0.025	-0.135	-0.783	-0.044	-0.050	0.975
Oils and fats	-0.018	-0.050	0.008	-0.020	-0.013	0.012	-0.032	-0.011	-0.804	0.007	1.019
NEC incl. sugar	-0.037	0.012	0.003	0.015	-0.066	-0.031	-0.028	-0.041	0.009	-0.784	0.896
Expenditure shares	0.177	0.030	0.101	0.093	0.061	0.142	0.063	0.192	0.035	0.108	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table 8: Quintile 5: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.720	0.025	-0.093	-0.031	-0.093	-0.021	-0.042	-0.015	-0.064	-0.038	0.949
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.012	-0.946	-0.071	-0.004	-0.000	0.000	-0.008	0.030	-0.046	0.011	1.011
Vegetables	-0.036	-0.129	-0.752	-0.007	-0.015	0.038	-0.052	-0.085	0.029	0.031	1.148
Fruits	-0.010	-0.008	-0.017	-0.852	-0.024	-0.004	-0.048	-0.038	-0.024	0.023	1.061
Fish and seafood	-0.079	-0.003	-0.027	-0.030	-0.695	-0.070	-0.010	-0.026	-0.053	-0.046	1.025
Milk and dairy	-0.020	-0.006	0.015	-0.021	-0.071	-0.851	-0.020	-0.002	0.029	-0.020	0.923
Poultry and Eggs	-0.019	-0.012	-0.044	-0.035	-0.008	-0.010	-0.619	-0.049	-0.041	-0.010	0.978
Meat	-0.013	0.095	-0.184	-0.074	-0.042	0.008	-0.124	-0.732	-0.044	-0.054	0.974
Oils and fats	-0.021	-0.045	0.013	-0.013	-0.022	0.017	-0.030	-0.011	-0.843	0.011	1.038
NEC incl. sugar	-0.042	0.018	0.012	0.007	-0.054	-0.031	-0.026	-0.047	0.020	-0.778	0.870
Expenditure shares	0.169	0.028	0.104	0.102	0.067	0.143	0.060	0.182	0.034	0.111	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

A Online Appendix

Table A1: EU26: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities for alternative food groups

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Fruits and vegetables	Veg. oils and fats	Milk and dairy	Fish and seafood	Beef	Pork	Poultry	Other meat/animal products	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.753	-0.026	-0.043	-0.013	-0.096	-0.015	-0.043	-0.003	-0.031	-0.025	0.944
Fruits and vegetables	-0.001	-0.886	-0.009	0.027	-0.009	-0.038	-0.072	-0.028	-0.094	0.057	1.075
Veg. oils and fats	-0.009	-0.002	-0.914	0.011	0.003	0.015	-0.000	-0.019	-0.029	-0.001	1.043
Milk and dairy	-0.008	0.002	0.018	-0.874	-0.085	-0.022	-0.005	0.022	0.014	-0.018	0.964
Fish and seafood	-0.076	-0.016	0.001	-0.081	-0.638	0.003	-0.049	0.025	-0.045	-0.060	0.961
Beef	-0.024	-0.040	0.021	-0.032	-0.006	-0.534	-0.149	-0.013	-0.070	-0.069	0.852
Pork	-0.022	-0.033	-0.003	-0.005	-0.030	-0.102	-0.539	-0.127	0.017	-0.020	0.980
Poultry	0.001	-0.014	-0.025	0.014	0.016	-0.005	-0.122	-0.717	-0.049	-0.026	1.004
Other meat/animal products	-0.031	-0.086	-0.081	0.011	-0.050	-0.077	0.030	-0.095	-0.638	-0.019	0.942
NEC incl. sugar	-0.021	0.025	-0.011	-0.022	-0.065	-0.077	-0.031	-0.049	-0.016	-0.765	0.947
Expenditure shares	0.184	0.220	0.023	0.150	0.059	0.032	0.045	0.048	0.135	0.104	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, ycentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A2: Austria: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.844	0.015	-0.035	-0.004	-0.095	-0.036	-0.032	0.020	-0.052	-0.034	0.953
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.009	-0.963	-0.011	-0.003	-0.044	-0.003	-0.001	0.001	-0.015	0.025	1.082
Vegetables	-0.006	-0.030	-0.794	-0.007	-0.054	0.046	-0.040	-0.035	-0.039	-0.038	1.098
Fruits	0.005	-0.012	-0.012	-0.757	-0.037	0.009	-0.064	-0.067	-0.013	-0.014	1.046
Fish and seafood	-0.052	-0.087	-0.053	-0.038	-0.224	-0.015	-0.103	-0.045	-0.101	-0.092	0.882
Milk and dairy	-0.028	-0.031	0.033	-0.002	-0.014	-0.865	-0.069	-0.014	-0.012	-0.006	0.937
Poultry and Eggs	-0.017	-0.011	-0.042	-0.057	-0.099	-0.047	-0.482	-0.013	-0.097	-0.048	0.966
Meat	0.030	-0.013	-0.089	-0.133	-0.086	-0.012	-0.023	-0.816	-0.018	-0.026	1.000
Oils and fats	-0.017	-0.026	-0.022	-0.009	-0.072	-0.005	-0.069	-0.008	-0.612	-0.009	0.980
NEC incl. sugar	-0.034	0.076	-0.075	-0.035	-0.157	-0.010	-0.083	-0.025	-0.022	-0.693	0.934
Expenditure shares	0.198	0.024	0.103	0.099	0.031	0.137	0.059	0.178	0.032	0.139	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A3: Belgium: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.986	0.073	0.081	0.029	-0.028	0.023	0.004	-0.037	-0.013	-0.037	1.053
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.021	-0.973	0.009	0.007	-0.015	0.014	-0.035	-0.014	-0.026	0.001	1.066
Vegetables	0.058	0.022	-0.851	-0.033	-0.026	-0.029	-0.137	-0.037	-0.045	0.017	1.118
Fruits	0.028	0.020	-0.032	-0.957	-0.006	-0.048	-0.024	-0.004	-0.004	0.019	1.118
Fish and seafood	-0.040	-0.054	-0.054	-0.028	-0.663	-0.028	-0.039	-0.027	-0.022	-0.036	0.850
Milk and dairy	0.006	0.022	-0.047	-0.069	-0.014	-0.883	-0.039	0.013	-0.011	-0.000	0.975
Poultry and Eggs	-0.002	-0.054	-0.093	-0.020	-0.018	-0.025	-0.607	-0.001	-0.018	-0.027	0.969
Meat	-0.069	-0.084	-0.112	-0.040	-0.029	0.018	-0.006	-0.729	-0.075	-0.092	0.928
Oils and fats	-0.006	-0.030	-0.023	-0.005	-0.008	-0.006	-0.015	-0.015	-0.709	-0.008	0.966
NEC incl. sugar	-0.062	-0.008	0.005	-0.001	-0.043	-0.011	-0.071	-0.076	-0.042	-0.761	0.924
Expenditure shares	0.180	0.034	0.099	0.092	0.069	0.120	0.043	0.198	0.032	0.134	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A4: Bulgaria: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.822	-0.020	-0.016	0.011	-0.221	-0.082	-0.048	0.002	-0.236	0.018	1.015
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.004	-1.032	-0.022	-0.014	0.014	0.002	-0.000	0.024	-0.012	-0.002	1.178
Vegetables	0.017	-0.124	-0.941	-0.063	-0.055	0.055	-0.029	-0.059	0.027	0.027	1.175
Fruits	0.021	-0.047	-0.035	-0.904	0.070	-0.034	-0.045	-0.013	0.026	0.023	1.130
Fish and seafood	-0.040	0.027	-0.014	0.030	-0.472	0.004	-0.057	-0.052	-0.012	0.007	1.055
Milk and dairy	-0.103	-0.030	0.042	-0.103	-0.007	-0.996	-0.052	0.106	0.130	0.035	0.947
Poultry and Eggs	-0.016	-0.006	-0.023	-0.047	-0.077	-0.019	-0.539	-0.042	-0.073	0.001	1.018
Meat	0.003	0.150	-0.124	-0.048	-0.285	0.127	-0.141	-0.918	-0.052	0.024	0.991
Oils and fats	-0.062	-0.029	0.002	0.005	-0.016	0.035	-0.049	-0.009	-0.743	-0.006	1.010
NEC incl. sugar	-0.017	-0.067	-0.043	0.003	-0.006	-0.039	-0.056	-0.029	-0.065	-0.712	0.586
Expenditure shares	0.175	0.021	0.138	0.065	0.022	0.175	0.063	0.195	0.040	0.104	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A5: Cyprus: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.342	0.031	-0.230	-0.028	-0.128	-0.058	-0.292	-0.184	-0.101	-0.016	0.863
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.013	-1.059	-0.004	-0.004	-0.002	0.000	-0.030	0.019	-0.012	0.013	1.061
Vegetables	-0.094	-0.009	-0.593	-0.035	0.021	0.019	-0.141	-0.053	0.038	-0.034	1.133
Fruits	0.015	0.002	-0.033	-0.924	-0.007	-0.015	-0.074	-0.032	0.060	0.023	1.182
Fish and seafood	-0.073	-0.022	-0.001	-0.023	-0.499	-0.014	-0.061	-0.101	-0.006	-0.047	0.869
Milk and dairy	-0.043	-0.019	-0.019	-0.069	-0.006	-0.815	-0.074	-0.028	0.039	-0.023	0.904
Poultry and Eggs	-0.133	-0.071	-0.111	-0.057	-0.046	-0.015	-0.318	-0.009	-0.048	-0.068	1.174
Meat	-0.157	0.075	-0.094	-0.064	-0.147	0.003	-0.028	-0.653	0.027	-0.072	1.094
Oils and fats	-0.026	-0.021	0.027	0.032	0.004	0.024	-0.033	0.014	-1.074	-0.004	1.078
NEC incl. sugar	-0.023	0.031	-0.074	-0.012	-0.059	-0.034	-0.123	-0.068	-0.002	-0.518	0.745
Expenditure shares	0.206	0.025	0.112	0.103	0.047	0.180	0.067	0.136	0.029	0.096	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A6: Czechia: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.586	-0.011	-0.101	-0.144	-0.122	-0.018	-0.152	-0.053	-0.242	-0.045	0.908
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.020	-1.131	-0.033	-0.007	-0.023	0.008	-0.025	0.011	0.009	0.032	1.477
Vegetables	-0.024	-0.091	-0.929	0.047	0.041	0.033	-0.035	-0.029	0.046	-0.032	1.197
Fruits	-0.048	-0.035	0.053	-0.897	0.015	0.002	-0.064	-0.036	0.082	0.047	1.181
Fish and seafood	-0.046	-0.049	0.010	-0.010	-0.636	0.007	-0.014	-0.017	-0.018	-0.030	0.744
Milk and dairy	-0.028	-0.061	0.021	-0.061	0.059	-0.922	-0.089	0.059	0.038	-0.067	0.847
Poultry and Eggs	-0.065	-0.095	-0.053	-0.073	-0.006	-0.032	-0.556	0.024	-0.080	-0.092	1.066
Meat	-0.031	-0.033	-0.099	-0.109	-0.012	0.101	0.056	-0.985	-0.061	-0.002	1.064
Oils and fats	-0.072	-0.017	0.014	0.036	-0.006	0.013	-0.051	-0.023	-0.667	-0.013	0.923
NEC incl. sugar	-0.029	0.044	-0.081	0.037	-0.053	-0.040	-0.135	-0.015	-0.029	-0.714	0.918
Expenditure shares	0.180	0.022	0.069	0.074	0.031	0.182	0.078	0.207	0.049	0.107	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A7: Germany: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.650	0.099	-0.141	-0.082	-0.173	0.016	-0.186	0.001	-0.176	-0.020	0.976
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.021	-0.973	-0.015	-0.015	-0.003	0.007	-0.007	-0.004	-0.031	0.009	1.026
Vegetables	-0.088	-0.047	-0.723	0.013	-0.003	0.062	-0.067	-0.057	-0.019	-0.057	1.079
Fruits	-0.047	-0.048	0.026	-0.866	-0.008	-0.019	-0.041	-0.039	0.001	-0.001	1.155
Fish and seafood	-0.077	-0.012	-0.014	-0.016	-0.676	-0.013	0.009	0.001	-0.005	-0.024	0.894
Milk and dairy	0.005	0.018	0.052	-0.052	-0.012	-0.947	-0.079	0.011	0.036	-0.031	0.917
Poultry and Eggs	-0.066	-0.016	-0.039	-0.026	0.009	-0.031	-0.518	-0.005	-0.052	-0.013	0.973
Meat	-0.011	-0.036	-0.131	-0.087	0.014	0.017	-0.016	-0.786	-0.023	-0.067	0.930
Oils and fats	-0.055	-0.050	-0.016	-0.009	-0.004	0.009	-0.046	-0.009	-0.580	-0.015	0.879
NEC incl. sugar	-0.009	0.038	-0.078	-0.016	-0.038	-0.019	-0.023	-0.043	-0.029	-0.812	1.032
Expenditure shares	0.180	0.026	0.108	0.114	0.038	0.155	0.041	0.175	0.035	0.128	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A8: Denmark: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.619	0.045	-0.136	0.013	-0.124	-0.074	-0.140	-0.078	-0.008	0.009	0.908
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.015	-0.957	-0.001	0.010	-0.015	-0.027	-0.003	0.004	-0.034	0.006	0.993
Vegetables	-0.061	0.025	-0.844	-0.049	-0.014	0.146	0.079	0.043	-0.163	-0.131	1.198
Fruits	0.018	0.030	-0.073	-0.844	-0.027	-0.001	-0.070	-0.034	0.068	-0.013	1.016
Fish and seafood	-0.081	-0.059	-0.043	-0.029	-0.115	-0.047	-0.174	-0.121	-0.123	-0.059	0.843
Milk and dairy	-0.068	-0.101	0.152	-0.017	-0.051	-0.818	-0.074	-0.047	0.065	-0.017	0.892
Poultry and Eggs	-0.061	0.001	0.061	-0.042	-0.132	-0.033	-0.529	0.044	-0.083	-0.084	1.149
Meat	-0.081	0.029	0.054	-0.051	-0.203	-0.041	0.070	-0.700	0.023	-0.149	1.054
Oils and fats	-0.003	-0.039	-0.079	0.022	-0.053	0.021	-0.053	0.004	-0.631	-0.009	0.933
NEC incl. sugar	0.033	0.033	-0.290	-0.028	-0.108	-0.019	-0.255	-0.170	-0.048	-0.558	1.006
Expenditure shares	0.154	0.033	0.097	0.091	0.053	0.145	0.050	0.176	0.028	0.172	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A9: Estonia: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.521	0.025	-0.152	-0.096	-0.087	-0.080	-0.142	-0.056	-0.123	-0.003	0.919
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.009	-0.987	-0.043	-0.011	-0.016	0.010	-0.025	-0.000	-0.007	0.035	0.970
Vegetables	-0.073	-0.084	-0.728	0.012	-0.025	0.014	-0.049	-0.016	-0.038	-0.011	1.088
Fruits	-0.053	-0.016	0.020	-0.808	-0.049	-0.044	-0.030	-0.030	0.007	0.006	1.127
Fish and seafood	-0.073	-0.049	-0.046	-0.056	-0.507	-0.054	-0.053	-0.014	0.018	-0.058	0.814
Milk and dairy	-0.068	0.037	0.002	-0.070	-0.052	-0.799	-0.037	-0.032	0.049	0.006	0.978
Poultry and Eggs	-0.056	-0.031	-0.037	-0.020	-0.024	-0.014	-0.695	0.001	0.007	0.003	1.028
Meat	-0.047	0.005	-0.040	-0.058	0.005	-0.023	0.002	-0.836	-0.030	-0.052	1.051
Oils and fats	-0.036	-0.008	-0.021	-0.002	0.010	0.012	-0.003	-0.009	-0.634	-0.055	0.957
NEC incl. sugar	0.000	0.137	-0.044	-0.018	-0.069	0.002	0.002	-0.059	-0.206	-0.814	0.944
Expenditure shares	0.156	0.027	0.083	0.113	0.055	0.154	0.042	0.177	0.027	0.165	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A10: Greece: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.647	0.042	-0.030	-0.012	-0.096	-0.027	-0.123	-0.097	-0.099	0.006	0.987
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.010	-0.908	-0.020	-0.008	-0.016	0.006	-0.009	0.003	-0.005	0.008	1.027
Vegetables	0.002	-0.068	-0.734	-0.046	-0.021	-0.012	-0.077	-0.073	0.017	-0.035	1.188
Fruits	0.001	-0.022	-0.045	-0.829	-0.005	-0.017	-0.037	-0.010	-0.003	-0.003	1.063
Fish and seafood	-0.077	-0.064	-0.043	-0.026	-0.394	-0.056	-0.099	-0.105	-0.053	0.011	0.858
Milk and dairy	-0.029	0.016	-0.051	-0.044	-0.065	-0.898	0.017	0.022	0.039	-0.008	0.948
Poultry and Eggs	-0.061	-0.024	-0.061	-0.036	-0.065	0.012	-0.581	-0.001	-0.009	-0.038	0.985
Meat	-0.112	0.010	-0.143	-0.032	-0.167	0.038	0.000	-0.661	-0.070	-0.066	1.009
Oils and fats	-0.069	-0.024	-0.009	-0.017	-0.043	0.018	-0.018	-0.043	-0.681	-0.023	0.898
NEC incl. sugar	-0.006	0.015	-0.053	-0.014	0.013	-0.013	-0.058	-0.044	-0.034	-0.749	0.897
Expenditure shares	0.162	0.024	0.127	0.086	0.073	0.146	0.067	0.174	0.073	0.070	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A11: Spain: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.798	0.056	-0.012	-0.010	-0.064	-0.013	-0.059	-0.054	-0.022	0.000	0.903
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.023	-1.097	0.003	0.019	-0.012	0.006	-0.016	-0.002	0.002	0.007	1.065
Vegetables	0.013	0.007	-0.969	-0.006	-0.009	0.006	-0.053	0.001	0.045	-0.018	1.089
Fruits	0.013	0.046	-0.015	-0.986	-0.029	-0.009	-0.024	0.008	0.039	0.002	1.035
Fish and seafood	-0.066	-0.052	-0.027	-0.042	-0.793	-0.039	-0.023	-0.018	0.005	-0.033	0.988
Milk and dairy	-0.000	0.007	-0.004	-0.016	-0.026	-0.974	-0.013	0.009	0.007	0.020	0.984
Poultry and Eggs	-0.019	-0.028	-0.039	-0.011	-0.008	-0.003	-0.800	-0.003	0.014	-0.032	1.060
Meat	-0.061	-0.017	-0.011	0.010	-0.017	0.024	-0.014	-0.879	0.029	-0.127	1.020
Oils and fats	0.002	0.005	0.034	0.024	0.007	0.012	0.018	0.013	-1.150	-0.021	1.098
NEC incl. sugar	-0.010	0.007	-0.047	-0.017	-0.037	0.007	-0.075	-0.094	-0.065	-0.641	0.843
Expenditure shares	0.155	0.028	0.095	0.117	0.121	0.114	0.057	0.193	0.021	0.099	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A12: Finland: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.484	-0.017	-0.288	-0.134	-0.089	-0.073	-0.123	-0.097	-0.300	0.048	0.917
Potatoes, roots, tubers	-0.003	-0.518	-0.077	-0.028	0.009	-0.003	-0.021	-0.029	-0.163	0.026	0.971
Vegetables	-0.136	-0.197	-0.726	-0.043	0.010	0.044	-0.073	-0.070	-0.159	0.082	1.127
Fruits	-0.071	-0.073	-0.051	-0.743	-0.020	-0.086	-0.038	-0.063	-0.035	0.067	1.136
Fish and seafood	-0.066	-0.005	-0.014	-0.033	-0.575	-0.028	-0.033	-0.004	-0.018	-0.049	0.785
Milk and dairy	-0.066	-0.009	0.049	-0.144	-0.015	-0.893	-0.018	-0.015	-0.075	0.042	0.988
Poultry and Eggs	-0.041	-0.037	-0.054	-0.025	-0.012	-0.001	-0.867	-0.004	-0.018	0.029	1.063
Meat	-0.102	-0.136	-0.171	-0.126	0.020	-0.033	-0.028	-0.607	-0.067	-0.005	0.881
Oils and fats	-0.068	-0.215	-0.060	-0.015	-0.003	-0.016	-0.008	-0.015	-0.310	0.023	0.958
NEC incl. sugar	0.120	0.235	0.265	0.153	-0.111	0.102	0.147	0.023	0.187	-1.363	1.100
Expenditure shares	0.159	0.023	0.080	0.093	0.048	0.174	0.038	0.142	0.026	0.217	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A13: France: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.581	0.021	0.047	-0.025	-0.124	-0.042	-0.116	-0.109	-0.153	-0.004	0.934
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.022	-0.951	-0.030	0.012	-0.001	-0.003	0.002	-0.022	-0.033	0.015	1.102
Vegetables	0.032	-0.025	-0.993	-0.009	-0.002	0.015	0.010	-0.008	0.015	-0.000	1.007
Fruits	0.002	0.010	-0.013	-0.913	-0.005	-0.005	-0.011	-0.006	0.009	-0.005	1.038
Fish and seafood	-0.116	-0.030	-0.021	-0.027	-0.615	-0.030	-0.039	-0.029	-0.030	-0.014	0.808
Milk and dairy	-0.027	-0.022	0.030	-0.017	-0.012	-0.883	-0.008	-0.002	0.024	-0.006	0.970
Poultry and Eggs	-0.073	-0.005	0.015	-0.016	-0.021	-0.007	-0.738	-0.018	-0.028	-0.029	0.993
Meat	-0.139	-0.082	-0.040	-0.030	-0.015	-0.009	-0.040	-0.686	-0.054	-0.056	0.929
Oils and fats	-0.043	-0.023	0.010	0.005	-0.009	0.009	-0.014	-0.011	-0.730	-0.001	0.991
NEC incl. sugar	-0.012	0.005	-0.014	-0.018	-0.004	-0.015	-0.039	-0.038	-0.012	-0.808	0.908
Expenditure shares	0.267	0.069	0.042	0.066	0.072	0.127	0.058	0.175	0.024	0.100	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A14: Croatia: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.769	-0.031	-0.029	0.004	-0.062	0.025	-0.135	-0.037	-0.134	0.024	0.844
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.003	-1.056	-0.020	-0.001	-0.029	0.016	0.001	0.015	-0.022	0.022	1.121
Vegetables	0.018	-0.063	-0.805	-0.059	-0.085	0.013	0.011	-0.018	-0.069	-0.017	1.204
Fruits	0.026	-0.005	-0.059	-0.931	-0.012	0.006	-0.011	-0.022	0.040	0.017	1.093
Fish and seafood	-0.034	-0.081	-0.093	-0.026	-0.595	-0.004	-0.047	-0.045	0.061	-0.004	0.863
Milk and dairy	0.020	0.034	-0.025	-0.019	0.010	-0.871	-0.091	-0.030	0.008	0.021	0.849
Poultry and Eggs	-0.076	-0.007	-0.006	-0.017	-0.053	-0.062	-0.502	-0.055	-0.094	-0.072	1.024
Meat	-0.012	0.085	-0.078	-0.070	-0.087	0.001	-0.112	-0.825	-0.030	-0.061	1.072
Oils and fats	-0.041	-0.047	-0.043	0.018	0.047	0.007	-0.054	-0.011	-0.690	-0.009	0.958
NEC incl. sugar	0.021	0.050	-0.046	0.007	0.004	0.020	-0.083	-0.045	-0.027	-0.829	0.907
Expenditure shares	0.183	0.023	0.100	0.065	0.035	0.135	0.095	0.229	0.038	0.098	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A15: Hungary: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.657	0.034	-0.025	-0.023	-0.043	-0.054	-0.132	-0.035	-0.200	0.005	0.872
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.014	-1.099	-0.032	-0.001	0.009	0.007	-0.004	0.014	-0.012	0.022	1.078
Vegetables	0.020	-0.072	-1.055	-0.007	-0.032	0.019	0.008	0.018	0.092	-0.021	1.206
Fruits	0.007	0.004	-0.007	-1.050	0.022	0.012	-0.026	-0.003	0.048	0.011	1.179
Fish and seafood	-0.022	0.007	-0.029	0.002	-0.598	-0.004	-0.058	-0.015	0.013	-0.041	0.835
Milk and dairy	-0.053	-0.001	-0.031	-0.017	0.015	-0.844	-0.047	-0.008	-0.009	0.015	0.863
Poultry and Eggs	-0.078	-0.010	0.001	-0.032	-0.114	-0.023	-0.605	-0.057	-0.023	-0.087	1.121
Meat	-0.028	0.052	-0.008	-0.042	-0.032	0.014	-0.137	-0.902	0.023	-0.005	0.999
Oils and fats	-0.067	-0.018	0.041	0.019	0.018	0.007	-0.014	0.009	-0.932	-0.017	1.059
NEC incl. sugar	-0.009	0.025	-0.061	-0.028	-0.080	0.004	-0.108	-0.021	-0.059	-0.680	0.798
Expenditure shares	0.170	0.026	0.097	0.076	0.011	0.148	0.089	0.230	0.046	0.106	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A16: Ireland: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.734	0.019	-0.090	-0.124	-0.060	-0.096	-0.040	-0.029	-0.161	0.007	0.987
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.020	-0.890	-0.040	-0.051	-0.020	-0.035	-0.029	0.006	-0.031	0.021	1.105
Vegetables	-0.027	-0.029	-0.839	0.032	0.017	0.043	-0.037	-0.035	-0.056	0.010	0.974
Fruits	-0.061	-0.056	0.058	-0.714	-0.006	0.018	-0.058	-0.061	0.004	0.008	1.038
Fish and seafood	-0.044	-0.039	0.016	-0.019	-0.564	-0.018	-0.045	-0.050	0.003	-0.039	0.771
Milk and dairy	-0.075	-0.071	0.100	0.012	0.001	-0.866	-0.001	-0.030	-0.008	0.034	0.940
Poultry and Eggs	-0.011	-0.026	-0.043	-0.045	-0.036	0.007	-0.828	0.003	-0.052	-0.001	1.072
Meat	-0.024	-0.003	-0.122	-0.129	-0.070	-0.027	0.000	-0.794	-0.004	-0.050	1.033
Oils and fats	-0.028	-0.014	-0.029	0.001	0.001	0.002	-0.022	0.000	-0.711	-0.001	1.051
NEC incl. sugar	-0.004	0.003	0.016	-0.001	-0.036	0.032	-0.012	-0.042	-0.035	-0.906	0.916
Expenditure shares	0.206	0.097	0.044	0.072	0.036	0.141	0.059	0.195	0.024	0.126	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A17: Italy: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.425	0.092	-0.108	-0.012	-0.132	-0.012	-0.190	-0.244	-0.065	-0.003	0.902
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.018	-1.088	0.005	0.007	-0.006	-0.004	-0.012	0.003	-0.003	0.007	0.976
Vegetables	-0.044	0.033	-0.708	0.009	-0.041	0.006	-0.012	-0.161	0.073	0.009	1.132
Fruits	0.006	0.028	-0.005	-0.848	-0.010	-0.001	-0.028	-0.089	0.027	0.019	1.020
Fish and seafood	-0.095	-0.020	-0.050	-0.012	-0.504	-0.040	-0.078	-0.146	-0.043	-0.031	1.037
Milk and dairy	-0.012	-0.024	-0.028	-0.020	-0.048	-0.798	-0.058	-0.021	-0.017	-0.004	0.890
Poultry and Eggs	-0.084	-0.034	-0.020	-0.025	-0.051	-0.031	-0.196	-0.123	-0.006	-0.069	0.947
Meat	-0.254	0.018	-0.265	-0.159	-0.202	-0.013	-0.292	-0.077	-0.063	-0.218	0.990
Oils and fats	-0.012	-0.004	0.052	0.030	-0.018	0.004	0.007	-0.019	-1.037	0.000	1.143
NEC incl. sugar	0.001	0.024	-0.005	0.010	-0.025	-0.000	-0.087	-0.113	-0.008	-0.664	0.953
Expenditure shares	0.189	0.016	0.132	0.105	0.086	0.137	0.062	0.174	0.032	0.066	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A18: Lithuania: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.594	-0.055	0.010	-0.005	-0.082	-0.053	-0.100	-0.082	-0.143	-0.036	0.813
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.006	-1.005	-0.033	-0.036	0.027	0.002	-0.021	0.005	-0.037	0.038	1.213
Vegetables	0.017	-0.023	-0.991	0.005	-0.008	0.007	-0.007	-0.000	-0.008	0.000	1.118
Fruits	0.016	-0.037	-0.010	-0.881	-0.019	0.037	-0.064	-0.017	0.005	-0.007	1.005
Fish and seafood	-0.039	0.009	-0.017	-0.022	-0.659	-0.011	-0.050	-0.045	0.017	-0.001	0.926
Milk and dairy	-0.037	-0.038	-0.011	0.045	-0.020	-0.901	-0.063	0.000	0.020	0.002	0.905
Poultry and Eggs	-0.042	-0.027	-0.018	-0.054	-0.051	-0.032	-0.433	-0.072	0.017	-0.032	0.983
Meat	-0.083	-0.019	-0.023	-0.047	-0.128	0.032	-0.205	-0.826	0.006	-0.076	1.079
Oils and fats	-0.047	-0.035	-0.013	-0.000	0.007	0.004	0.006	-0.006	-0.696	-0.022	0.863
NEC incl. sugar	-0.010	0.016	-0.011	-0.009	0.008	0.010	-0.046	-0.037	-0.042	-0.851	0.984
Expenditure shares	0.165	0.082	0.039	0.066	0.054	0.140	0.062	0.252	0.044	0.096	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A19: Luxembourg: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.945	-0.017	0.018	-0.022	-0.005	0.000	0.021	-0.035	-0.014	0.010	0.953
Potatoes, roots, tubers	-0.003	-0.960	0.012	0.000	-0.002	0.021	-0.019	-0.003	-0.058	0.005	0.940
Vegetables	0.033	0.051	-0.912	-0.026	0.007	0.032	-0.116	-0.017	-0.090	0.004	1.082
Fruits	0.001	-0.003	-0.026	-0.830	-0.017	-0.010	-0.054	-0.009	-0.038	-0.002	1.087
Fish and seafood	-0.018	-0.007	-0.010	-0.039	-0.710	-0.018	-0.051	-0.049	-0.018	-0.029	0.859
Milk and dairy	0.002	0.064	0.026	-0.026	-0.003	-0.886	-0.117	-0.028	-0.053	0.021	0.986
Poultry and Eggs	0.013	-0.039	-0.092	-0.038	-0.027	-0.074	-0.651	0.001	0.053	-0.030	0.985
Meat	-0.031	0.012	-0.044	-0.053	-0.061	-0.040	0.021	-0.864	-0.024	-0.030	1.033
Oils and fats	-0.007	-0.054	-0.040	-0.016	-0.005	-0.025	0.036	-0.007	-0.731	-0.001	0.969
NEC incl. sugar	0.001	0.012	-0.014	-0.037	-0.037	0.014	-0.055	-0.021	0.003	-0.830	0.881
Expenditure shares	0.183	0.027	0.101	0.102	0.073	0.131	0.059	0.184	0.023	0.117	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, unvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A20: Latvia: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.614	-0.017	-0.074	-0.008	-0.079	-0.023	-0.126	-0.105	-0.125	0.027	0.872
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.006	-1.026	-0.057	-0.003	-0.001	0.006	-0.009	0.023	-0.018	0.023	1.115
Vegetables	-0.017	-0.133	-0.790	-0.028	-0.012	-0.008	-0.025	0.015	-0.086	-0.034	1.216
Fruits	0.012	-0.014	-0.050	-0.852	0.005	-0.016	-0.018	-0.033	0.017	-0.004	1.035
Fish and seafood	-0.051	-0.004	-0.030	-0.004	-0.647	-0.011	-0.027	-0.037	-0.020	-0.054	0.906
Milk and dairy	-0.018	-0.008	-0.058	-0.031	-0.008	-0.870	-0.068	0.021	0.079	-0.039	0.914
Poultry and Eggs	-0.063	-0.021	-0.031	-0.016	-0.021	-0.032	-0.515	-0.042	-0.019	-0.043	0.972
Meat	-0.113	0.087	0.002	-0.070	-0.061	0.066	-0.091	-0.864	0.044	-0.079	1.081
Oils and fats	-0.042	-0.025	-0.048	0.000	-0.012	0.019	-0.014	0.001	-0.700	-0.023	0.876
NEC incl. sugar	0.027	0.048	-0.079	-0.023	-0.069	-0.044	-0.080	-0.060	-0.048	-0.657	0.885
Expenditure shares	0.158	0.030	0.101	0.075	0.047	0.166	0.061	0.211	0.037	0.113	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A21: Malta: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.379	0.097	-0.114	-0.066	-0.235	-0.020	-0.211	-0.169	-0.106	-0.048	0.871
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.020	-1.160	-0.010	-0.014	-0.006	0.008	0.009	-0.003	0.012	0.025	0.910
Vegetables	-0.033	-0.009	-0.717	-0.038	-0.096	0.021	-0.144	0.037	0.007	0.002	1.147
Fruits	-0.025	-0.028	-0.066	-0.846	-0.001	-0.002	0.004	-0.052	0.031	0.029	1.032
Fish and seafood	-0.143	-0.020	-0.121	-0.002	0.131	-0.047	-0.285	-0.170	-0.086	-0.171	1.004
Milk and dairy	-0.011	0.029	-0.005	-0.018	-0.065	-0.919	-0.121	0.063	0.039	-0.003	0.903
Poultry and Eggs	-0.093	0.046	-0.147	0.009	-0.235	-0.065	-0.231	0.022	-0.054	-0.094	1.125
Meat	-0.157	0.003	0.047	-0.072	-0.273	0.106	0.028	-0.716	0.070	-0.120	1.060
Oils and fats	-0.025	0.025	-0.005	0.007	-0.028	0.016	-0.027	0.016	-0.846	-0.014	0.966
NEC incl. sugar	-0.025	0.108	-0.009	0.007	-0.196	0.000	-0.147	-0.087	-0.031	-0.540	0.933
Expenditure shares	0.192	0.023	0.092	0.114	0.065	0.148	0.071	0.164	0.031	0.100	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A22: Netherlands: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.723	0.067	0.025	-0.061	-0.072	0.019	-0.039	-0.113	-0.101	-0.027	1.048
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.024	-0.538	-0.012	-0.033	-0.128	-0.010	-0.005	-0.006	-0.187	-0.000	0.992
Vegetables	0.017	-0.013	-0.490	-0.016	-0.085	0.007	-0.093	-0.176	-0.137	-0.014	1.033
Fruits	-0.041	-0.038	-0.007	-0.165	-0.133	-0.020	-0.124	-0.311	-0.190	-0.002	1.092
Fish and seafood	-0.071	-0.236	-0.104	-0.141	0.399	-0.022	-0.120	-0.236	-0.467	-0.057	0.695
Milk and dairy	0.003	-0.024	-0.005	-0.044	0.005	-0.807	-0.007	-0.061	-0.037	0.003	0.946
Poultry and Eggs	-0.040	-0.018	-0.081	-0.100	-0.085	-0.020	-0.101	-0.097	-0.120	-0.025	0.768
Meat	-0.137	-0.042	-0.261	-0.426	-0.325	-0.081	-0.179	0.362	-0.417	-0.119	0.877
Oils and fats	-0.030	-0.142	-0.062	-0.079	-0.223	-0.010	-0.073	-0.129	0.655	-0.013	1.053
NEC incl. sugar	-0.050	-0.009	-0.036	-0.029	-0.048	-0.002	-0.027	-0.110	-0.053	-0.644	0.898
Expenditure shares	0.177	0.042	0.117	0.110	0.041	0.151	0.049	0.138	0.021	0.155	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A23: Poland: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.587	0.011	-0.107	-0.103	-0.087	-0.079	-0.136	-0.020	-0.159	-0.036	0.927
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.009	-1.003	-0.030	-0.025	-0.014	0.013	-0.009	0.003	-0.018	0.036	1.115
Vegetables	-0.053	-0.083	-0.845	0.015	0.012	0.028	-0.011	-0.012	0.012	-0.053	1.113
Fruits	-0.053	-0.064	0.010	-0.790	0.012	-0.003	-0.042	-0.037	0.011	-0.005	1.067
Fish and seafood	-0.043	-0.033	-0.007	-0.004	-0.527	-0.027	-0.048	-0.039	-0.008	-0.030	0.819
Milk and dairy	-0.057	0.021	0.013	-0.016	-0.033	-0.912	-0.036	0.023	-0.003	-0.011	0.962
Poultry and Eggs	-0.058	-0.024	-0.007	-0.034	-0.046	-0.015	-0.624	-0.033	0.006	-0.027	1.074
Meat	-0.003	-0.010	-0.045	-0.087	-0.091	0.060	-0.097	-0.830	-0.033	-0.108	1.040
Oils and fats	-0.048	-0.030	-0.001	0.000	-0.001	-0.003	-0.003	-0.012	-0.661	-0.029	0.934
NEC incl. sugar	-0.034	0.097	-0.094	-0.025	-0.044	-0.022	-0.067	-0.083	-0.081	-0.630	0.893
Expenditure shares	0.168	0.029	0.106	0.081	0.035	0.122	0.071	0.220	0.045	0.124	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A24: Portugal: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.636	0.066	-0.046	-0.041	-0.107	-0.002	-0.103	-0.034	-0.079	0.028	0.829
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.031	-1.088	-0.037	0.013	-0.013	0.019	0.003	0.004	-0.009	0.015	1.078
Vegetables	0.000	-0.062	-0.776	-0.033	-0.060	0.043	-0.037	-0.011	-0.003	0.026	1.135
Fruits	0.006	0.033	-0.051	-0.824	-0.045	0.019	-0.024	-0.036	-0.006	0.014	1.067
Fish and seafood	-0.130	-0.064	-0.171	-0.085	-0.538	-0.038	-0.134	-0.092	-0.064	-0.037	0.984
Milk and dairy	0.002	0.027	0.025	-0.003	-0.026	-0.952	-0.030	0.014	-0.021	0.017	0.861
Poultry and Eggs	-0.058	0.005	-0.052	-0.024	-0.070	-0.014	-0.547	-0.054	-0.025	-0.023	1.028
Meat	-0.023	0.008	-0.044	-0.064	-0.076	0.052	-0.095	-0.771	-0.074	-0.041	1.044
Oils and fats	-0.033	-0.018	0.008	0.004	-0.023	0.004	-0.032	-0.033	-0.857	-0.015	1.164
NEC incl. sugar	0.012	0.016	0.007	-0.009	-0.027	0.008	-0.028	-0.031	-0.025	-0.838	0.854
Expenditure shares	0.202	0.031	0.080	0.106	0.120	0.136	0.064	0.154	0.040	0.066	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A25: Romania: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.889	-0.023	-0.024	0.066	-0.081	-0.059	-0.024	-0.020	-0.065	0.015	1.061
Potatoes, roots, tubers	-0.004	-0.471	0.008	0.007	-0.037	0.003	-0.004	-0.005	-0.002	-0.135	1.022
Vegetables	-0.026	0.033	-0.833	-0.088	-0.009	-0.035	-0.021	-0.005	0.001	0.020	0.967
Fruits	0.041	0.050	-0.043	-0.596	-0.078	0.005	-0.046	-0.041	0.087	-0.266	1.143
Fish and seafood	-0.029	-0.090	-0.006	-0.061	-0.221	0.004	-0.028	-0.047	-0.088	-0.174	0.934
Milk and dairy	-0.049	0.018	-0.032	-0.002	0.030	-0.924	-0.000	0.021	-0.009	-0.046	1.070
Poultry and Eggs	-0.025	-0.027	-0.022	-0.077	-0.049	-0.015	-0.520	-0.056	-0.062	-0.163	0.917
Meat	-0.041	-0.054	-0.009	-0.137	-0.166	0.007	-0.106	-0.713	-0.016	-0.208	0.971
Oils and fats	-0.025	-0.008	-0.006	0.031	-0.065	-0.012	-0.029	-0.009	-0.682	0.011	0.816
NEC incl. sugar	-0.015	-0.449	-0.000	-0.285	-0.258	-0.044	-0.139	-0.095	0.020	0.157	0.788
Expenditure shares	0.187	0.021	0.123	0.068	0.040	0.152	0.102	0.203	0.041	0.065	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A26: Sweden: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.097	0.078	0.014	0.074	-0.423	-0.075	-0.117	-0.506	-0.019	-0.049	1.038
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.025	-0.843	-0.110	0.002	-0.017	0.007	-0.029	0.001	-0.018	0.010	1.081
Vegetables	0.016	-0.157	-0.964	0.047	0.016	0.024	0.035	-0.021	0.079	-0.002	1.130
Fruits	0.018	-0.002	0.033	-0.878	-0.029	0.000	-0.037	-0.052	-0.004	0.023	1.002
Fish and seafood	-0.285	-0.058	-0.003	-0.087	0.727	-0.030	-0.177	-0.377	-0.104	-0.375	0.827
Milk and dairy	-0.080	-0.001	0.015	-0.005	-0.026	-0.714	-0.129	-0.100	0.084	0.005	0.934
Poultry and Eggs	-0.028	-0.037	0.033	-0.037	-0.098	-0.046	-0.574	0.039	-0.113	-0.029	1.113
Meat	-0.528	-0.015	-0.095	-0.165	-0.535	-0.103	0.088	0.211	-0.115	-0.264	1.029
Oils and fats	-0.017	-0.016	0.029	-0.003	-0.023	0.017	-0.072	-0.032	-0.540	-0.037	0.848
NEC incl. sugar	-0.061	-0.031	-0.083	0.050	-0.420	-0.016	-0.101	-0.193	-0.098	-0.066	0.783
Expenditure shares	0.207	0.034	0.061	0.041	0.061	0.176	0.042	0.176	0.032	0.171	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A27: Slovenia: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.637	0.052	-0.055	-0.050	-0.027	-0.049	-0.098	-0.077	-0.099	0.016	0.906
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.028	-1.048	0.010	0.002	-0.013	0.010	0.015	-0.021	-0.001	-0.002	1.111
Vegetables	-0.031	0.013	-0.799	-0.009	-0.024	-0.014	-0.019	-0.008	-0.021	-0.046	1.008
Fruits	-0.029	-0.001	-0.008	-0.844	0.032	0.001	-0.053	-0.044	0.034	-0.019	1.019
Fish and seafood	-0.040	-0.021	-0.042	-0.001	-0.555	-0.020	-0.036	-0.037	-0.022	-0.033	0.694
Milk and dairy	-0.040	0.006	-0.022	-0.006	0.007	-0.966	-0.011	0.051	0.006	-0.008	0.952
Poultry and Eggs	-0.054	0.019	-0.013	-0.034	-0.039	-0.002	-0.630	-0.058	-0.024	-0.021	1.039
Meat	-0.071	-0.097	-0.002	-0.063	-0.041	0.098	-0.135	-0.817	-0.127	-0.024	1.096
Oils and fats	-0.041	-0.004	-0.011	0.021	-0.009	0.010	-0.022	-0.047	-0.820	0.020	1.045
NEC incl. sugar	0.009	-0.029	-0.067	-0.036	-0.025	-0.020	-0.051	-0.037	0.029	-0.756	0.873
Expenditure shares	0.169	0.019	0.110	0.110	0.025	0.140	0.056	0.198	0.040	0.131	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.

Table A28: Slovakia: Uncompensated price and expenditure elasticities

	Price elasticities										Expenditure elasticities
	Bread and cereals	Potatoes, roots, tubers	Vegetables	Fruits	Fish and seafood	Milk and dairy	Poultry and Eggs	Meat	Oils and fats	NEC incl. sugar	
Bread and cereals	-0.644	0.017	-0.022	-0.048	-0.063	-0.096	-0.142	-0.049	-0.175	-0.026	0.913
Potatoes, roots, tubers	0.008	-1.051	-0.022	-0.004	0.004	0.009	-0.022	0.005	-0.012	0.022	1.029
Vegetables	0.014	-0.044	-1.017	-0.040	-0.015	0.069	-0.084	-0.001	0.011	0.014	1.196
Fruits	-0.011	-0.007	-0.051	-0.943	-0.006	0.015	-0.028	-0.012	0.005	0.017	1.122
Fish and seafood	-0.030	0.006	-0.022	-0.015	-0.508	-0.043	-0.032	-0.033	-0.011	-0.015	0.823
Milk and dairy	-0.087	0.023	0.064	-0.009	-0.095	-0.903	-0.078	0.039	-0.012	-0.012	0.908
Poultry and Eggs	-0.057	-0.042	-0.077	-0.026	-0.034	-0.031	-0.583	0.006	0.004	-0.041	1.043
Meat	-0.036	0.021	-0.035	-0.032	-0.085	0.082	0.016	-0.982	0.093	-0.037	1.049
Oils and fats	-0.051	-0.026	-0.006	-0.007	-0.006	-0.004	-0.002	0.016	-0.722	-0.037	0.923
NEC incl. sugar	-0.018	0.072	-0.009	0.000	-0.016	-0.006	-0.086	-0.038	-0.102	-0.834	0.950
Expenditure shares	0.172	0.028	0.089	0.095	0.030	0.152	0.064	0.203	0.043	0.124	

Note:

Estimation based on following configuration: 1, uvnonadj, ystone, uncensored, weighted, nmin1, yuncentered, actual, partial, pzintyes

NEC = Not elsewhere classified. Own-price elasticities in bold. For price elasticities, each column gives the percentage change in quantity demanded due to a one percent price increase of the good given in the respective row. Expenditure elasticities show the percentage change in quantity demanded for the good given in the respective row due to a one percent increase in total food expenditures.